

Liquid biopsy biomarkers for bladder cancer diagnostics: LiqBio-BC

Version 1

Description

DMP for a project that aims to development of an innovative diagnostic test (medical device) for non-invasive detection of bladder cancer, using epigenetic markers (miRNAs) from urinary exosomes, as well as to analyze clinical and demographic data with an artificial intelligence algorithm, thereby strengthening the knowledge base.

Bladder cancer (BC) is a common public health problem worldwide and a major cause of morbidity and mortality, resulting in significant treatment costs over the patient's lifetime. Due to the high tumours heterogeneity, there is poor risk stratification, emergence of treatment resistance, and ultimately poor clinical outcome.

The project aims to develop an innovative diagnostic test for early non-invasive bladder cancer diagnostics using epigenetic markers, isolated from urine exosomes. The test will increase healthy life years, reduce treatment costs, and enhance collective knowledge via AI.

Project's mission is to shift bladder cancer detection from hospitals to primary care, empowering earlier diagnosis, better treatment choice, higher survival rates and lower costs.

Funder

Latvian Council of Science

Grant

BioPhoT

Researchers

Zanda Daneberga (orcid:0000-0003-0887-2973), Miki Nakazawa-Miklasevica (0000-0001-8198-0060), Dmitrijs Bliznuks (0000-0003-4252-9220), Edvins Miklasevics (0000-0002-7817-4268), Egils Vjaters (0000-0003-0054-3745), JANIS GARDOVSKIS (0000-0001-9656-6209), Vilnis Lietuvietis (0000-0002-0619-3910), JURIS PLONIS (0000-0001-7345-7835), Ērika Bitiņa-Barlote (0000-0001-7859-3940), Mihails Šatcs (0009-0008-5866-2716), Sanda Siliņa

Organizations

Riga Stradiņš University, Riga Technical University

1. Main Info

Title of DMP: [Liquid biopsy biomarkers for bladder cancer diagnostics: LiqBio-BC](#)

Description:

DMP for a project that aims to development of an innovative diagnostic test (medical device) for non-invasive detection of bladder cancer, using epigenetic markers (miRNAs) from urinary exosomes, as well as to analyze clinical and demographic data with an artificial intelligence algorithm, thereby strengthening the knowledge base.

Bladder cancer (BC) is a common public health problem worldwide and a major cause of morbidity and mortality, resulting in significant treatment costs over the patient's lifetime. Due to the high tumours heterogeneity, there is poor risk stratification, emergence of treatment resistance, and ultimately poor clinical outcome.

The project aims to develop an innovative diagnostic test for early non-invasive bladder cancer diagnostics using epigenetic markers, isolated from urine exosomes. The test will increase healthy life years, reduce treatment costs, and enhance collective knowledge via AI.

Project's mission is to shift bladder cancer detection from hospitals to primary care, empowering earlier diagnosis, better treatment choice, higher survival rates and lower costs.

Researchers:

[Zanda Daneberga \(orcid:0000-0003-0887-2973\)](#)

[Miki Nakazawa-Miklasevica \(0000-0001-8198-0060\)](#)

[Dmitrijs Bliznuks \(0000-0003-4252-9220\)](#)

[Edvins Miklasevics \(0000-0002-7817-4268\)](#)

[Egils Vjaters \(0000-0003-0054-3745\)](#)

[JANIS GARDOVSKIS \(0000-0001-9656-6209\)](#)

[Vilnis Lietuvietis \(0000-0002-0619-3910\)](#)

[JURIS PLONIS \(0000-0001-7345-7835\)](#)

[Ērika Bitiņa-Barlote \(0000-0001-7859-3940\)](#)

[Mihails Šatcs \(0009-0008-5866-2716\)](#)

[Sanda Siliņa](#)

Organizations:

Riga Stradiņš University

Riga Technical University

Contact: Daneberga Zanda (Zanda.Daneberga@rsu.lv)

2. Funding

Funding organizations: Latvian Council of Science

Grants: BioPhoT

Project:

3. License

License: CC-BY-4.0

Access Rights: Public

4. Templates

Descriptions

miRNA biomarkers in bladder cancer

Dataset of case and control groups demographic data, clinical data and qPCR results (fold change) of target miRNAs. The main purpose is to development an innovative diagnostic test (medical device) for non-invasive detection of bladder cancer, using epigenetic markers (miRNAs) from urinary exosomes, as well as to analyze clinical and demographic data.

Template: [RSU DMP Template](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Data Summary

1.1 Purpose of data

1.1.1 What is the purpose of the data collection/generation?

The dataset consists of clinical, demographic data, qPCR results of bladder cancer patients and control subjects without oncological diseases. The main purpose is to development an innovative diagnostic test (medical device) for non-invasive detection of bladder cancer, using epigenetic markers (miRNAs) from urinary exosomes, as well as to analyze clinical and demographic data.

1.1.2 To whom the data might be useful ("data utility")?

Researchers, students.

1.2 Data characteristics

1.2.1 Type of data generated/collected

- Clinical data
- Experimental data

1.2.2 Format of data generated/collected

- CSV
- XLS

1.2.4 Are you re-using this dataset?

No

The study design is based on biomarker validation in prospective case and control group based on double blind principle.

2 Research Data Management

2.1 Metadata and documentation

2.1.1 Will data be attributed with standard identification mechanism (e.g. persistent and unique identifiers such as Digital Object Identifiers – DOI)?

Yes

DOI

2.1.2 Do you plan to provide metadata for your data?

Yes

2.1.3 Will you use any metadata standard?

Yes

DDI (Data Documentation Initiative)

2.1.4 Will search keywords be provided that optimize possibilities for re-use?

Yes

miRNAs nomenclature, ICD-10

2.1.5 Will you provide clear version numbers?

Yes

2.1.6 Will you document the dataset?

Yes

Codebook

2.2 Data accessibility

2.2.1 Are the data formats open to software applications and to recombination with different data sets?

Yes

"File.csv" is widely used file format, accessible for the wide range of software's.

2.2.2 What methods or software tools are needed to access the data?

"File.csv" is widely used file format, accessible for the wide range of software's. Generic methods and standard software tools are enough to access the data.

2.2.3 Is it possible to include the relevant software in the dataset (e.g. source code)?

No

2.2.4 Will you use data standard vocabulary/taxonomy/ontology to make your data interoperable?

Yes

miRNAs nomenclature, ICD-10

2.3 Data publishing and long-term preservation

2.3.2 How will the data be licensed to permit the widest re-use possible? Indicate the license planned to use

Creative Commons Attribution 4.0

An open licence that permits a wide re-use possibilities.

2.3.3 What type of access the dataset will have (choose one)?

restricted, request access (access is restricted, but request with collaboration proposal could be submitted to the authors)

The access request will be reviewed by authors with compliance of Riga Stradins University policy.

2.3.4 Will there be an embargo period for access to these data?

Yes

2035-01-01

The data sets are in use for the continues projects. The restriction applies till final publishing of the results or patent submission.

2.3.5 When data will be made available for re-use?

2035-01-01

2.3.6 Will you provide reference to the dataset in scientific publications and other research outputs?

Yes

3 Resources and Security

3.1 Allocation of resources and quality assurance

3.1.1 Which costs will be covered within this project for making data FAIR?

- Storage
- Archiving
- Re-use
- Security
- Processing
- Long-term preservation

3.1.2 Have you discussed how the costs will be covered?

RSU covers majority of costs except data processing that will be carried out by project personnel.

3.1.3 Which institutions are responsible for handling the data? Which institution(s) are the data controller in this project?

- Riga Stradinš University (RSU)
- Riga Technical University

1. Clinical and demographic data of study participants - RSU.
2. Data of miRNA expression level (miRNAs isolated from urinary exosomes) - RSU.
3. Machine learning based algorithm for sample stratification in cancer and non-cancer groups - RTU.

3.1.4 Who will be responsible for data management in your project? Which person will be the data manager responsible for the correct processing of data in the project, staff training, and maintenance of the data management plan?

Zanda Daneberga (orcid: [0000-0003-0887-2973](https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0887-2973))

Project scientific leader Zanda Daneberga is responsible for data management plan. The tasks related to data management will be delegated to the scientific

group. The study data in coded form will be stored in the RSU institutional Microsoft SharePoint environment. Access to these files are restricted to only authorized researchers involved in the study and requires dual authentication.

3.1.5 Who will collect and process the data for this study (name data processors- researchers, laboratory technicians, assistants, and other persons who will work with the data for this study)?

- Ērika Bitiņa-Barlote (0000-0001-7859-3940)
- Sanda Siliņa
- Miki Nakazawa-Miklasevica (0000-0001-8198-0060)
- Dmitrijs Bliznuks (0000-0003-4252-9220)

3.1.6 Are there data quality assurance processes foreseen?

Yes

The quality of data sets will be reviewed before the publishing in repository.

3.2 Data security

3.2.1 What security measures will be used for data security?

- Encryption
- Firewall
- Passwords
- Physical access control
- Other

Dual authentication

By using RSU IT infrastructure data encryption, firewall, passwords are ensured for all folders stored in RSU institutional Microsoft SharePoint.

To access user account with file access dual authentication is needed. A contract is signed between RSU and RTU (3-L-11/218/2025 - Par ilgtermiņa valsts pētījumu programmas "Inovāciju fonds – ilgtermiņa pētījumu programma" platformas "Biomedicīnas un fotonikas pētniecības platforma inovatīvu produktu radīšanai

(BioPhoT)", projekta Nr. OSI_PIP_BioPhoT-2025/1-0038) where RTU ensures that similar safety measures will be applied within RTU IT infrastructure.

3.2.2 What provisions are in place for data security?

- Data access
- Data storage
- Data recovery
- Data sharing

3.2.3 Where the data will be stored during research? For how long the data will be stored there?

Restricted access in RSU institutional Microsoft SharePoint (internal data storage infrastructure provided by RSU).

The project file folder will be managed by data manager (Zanda Daneberga). Data manager will grant access to study personnel depending on the current tasks of specific stages of the project.

Right after informed consent process and study participant enrolment, the gathered data will be pseudonymized. Pseudonymization key will be securely stored by those who participate in recruitment and informed consent process (Ērika Bitiņa-Barlote and Sanda Siliņa). The remaining project team will work with pseudonymized data only.

After the completion of the project in January 2030, the RSU IT Department will be contacted to permanently delete all research data that will no longer be planned for further research or that has not already been uploaded to RSU Dataverse.

3.2.4 When and how will data from the specified storage location be deleted or destroyed?

During the study, paper-based informed consent forms and questionnaires will be stored at the RSU Institute of Oncology and Molecular Genetics premises, Pilsoņu Street 13, Building 13, in a GDPR-compliant metal cabinet with restricted access, limited to researchers involved in the study. After the study is completed, the

informed consent forms will be transferred to the RSU Archive for storage for 75 years.

Electronic files are stored in the RSU institutional Microsoft SharePoint environment. Access to this file is restricted to researchers involved in the study and requires dual authentication.

After the completion of the project in January 2030, the RSU IT Department will be contacted to permanently delete research data that will no longer be planned for further research or that has not already been uploaded to RSU Dataverse.

3.2.5 Have you ensured that your chosen repository is appropriate for long term preservation and curation?

Yes

RSU Dataverse has all the necessary measures to ensure secure long term preservation and curation.

3.3 Ethical and legal aspects

3.3.1 Are there any ethical or legal issues that could have an impact on data collection and sharing?

Yes

The project was evaluated by the Central Medical Ethics committee and positive approval received. The informed consent was received from each study participant.

3.3.2 Have you got/will you get permission from ethics committee to collect and process data (if applicable)?

Yes

3.3.3 Is it planned to conduct an informed consent process for research subjects?

Yes

3.3.4 Where and for how long will the signed informed consent forms be stored? Who will have access to these documents?

Storage will be ensured according to the internal RSU regulation, national law and GDPR.

The informed consent forms and questionnaires in paper format will be stored during the study at the premises of the RSU Institute of Oncology and Molecular Genetics, Pilsoņu Street 13, Building 13, in a VDR-compliant metal cabinet with restricted access, available only to researchers involved in the study. After the study is completed, the informed consent forms will be transferred to the RSU Archive for storage for 75 years.

Clinical and demographic data, coded from the questionnaires, will be entered into an Excel file stored in the RSU institutional Microsoft SharePoint environment. Access to this file is restricted to researchers involved in the study and requires dual authentication.

Measurement data obtained during the study will be stored in the RSU institutional Microsoft SharePoint environment. Access to this file is restricted to researchers involved in the study and requires dual authentication. After the study is completed, the dataset will be deposited in the RSU institutional repository, DataVerse.

3.3.5 Is informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation included in questionnaires dealing with personal data (if applicable)?

In the informed consent forms, study participants are asked to allow the anonymous publication of their health status description and corresponding images (radiological examination images, photographs, etc.). As a result the data will be deposited with closed/restricted access as some of the data could carry a re-identification risk.

3.3.6 Will data collected/generated include personal data or any other sensitive information?

Yes

3.3.7 Is the collected/generated data intended to be processed outside the EU?

No

3.3.8 Is the collected/generated personal data intended to be used for profiling and/or automated decision-making?

No

3.3.9 Is artificial intelligence intended to be used in the processing of collected/generated sensitive or personal data?

Artificial intelligence will process only pseudonymized data. Data will be used for machine learning, to develop biomarker testing results and clinical data algorithm for stratification of cancer/non-cancer status at RTU. The RSU DPS specialists (Marina Siņkovska) will be consulted for data sharing and usage of machine learning algorithms at partner institution (RTU).

3.3.10 What methods do you intend to use to process and access the data securely?

- Data accompanied by informed consent statements
- National laws
- Pseudonymization

Powered by

